

Research On The Improvement Of Teachers' Practical Competency In Vocational Colleges Under Learning Motivation Theory

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
May 24, 2021

Accepted:
December 31, 2021

Keywords :

Theory Of Learning
Motivation; Teachers'
Practical Competency In
Vocational Colleges;
Promote

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5812196

Abstract

At this stage, the development of China's vocational education industry is entering a very critical stage. The improvement of teachers' practical competency has become an inevitable requirement. The development of vocational education should make new changes. Applying learning motivation theory to analyze the current situation of teachers' practical competency in vocational colleges, we can find that the current situation of teachers' practical competency in vocational colleges is not ideal, and there is an urgent need to start, deal with and deal with it from different angles. In terms of the arrangement of relevant educational work and the construction of teachers' team, including the cultivation of teachers' ethics, the training mode of teachers' practical competency in vocational colleges should be continuously improved, so as to promote the improvement of teachers' practical competency and achieve more outstanding achievements in the future. This paper discusses, analyzes and puts forward reasonable suggestions. The author conducted a questionnaire survey on some vocational college teachers, and analyzed the current situation of vocational college teachers' practical competency according to the survey results. In the context of the integration of industry and education, the author will also put forward some suggestions for the improvement of teachers' practical competency in Vocational Colleges recommendations

Introduction

In recent years, China's vocational education has developed rapidly, and vocational education has become an important part of China's higher education. By 2021, there are 2738 colleges and universities in China, an increase of 50 over the previous year. Among them, there are 1468 Vocational Colleges, an increase of 45 over the previous year. The total number of students in various types of higher education in China is 41.83 million, an increase of 1.81 million over the previous year. Among them, there are 8723 vocational (College) colleges. Premier Li Keqiang said in his government work report on March 5, 2019 that "Reform and improve the examination and enrollment methods of Vocational Colleges, encourage more fresh high school graduates and veterans, laid-off workers and migrant workers to apply for the examination, and expand the enrollment of 1 million people on a large scale this year." Vocational education has ushered in a new development opportunity in China. In China's higher education system, the proportion of vocational education is almost half, which has made a great contribution to the establishment and improvement of China's education system. With the rapid development of higher vocational education, the number of teachers in higher Vocational Colleges is also increasing. There were 2.6687 million faculty and workers in colleges and universities, an increase of 102000 over the previous year, an increase of 3.97%; There were 1.833 million full-time teachers, an increase of 92800 over the previous year, an increase of 5.34%. The ratio of students to teachers in colleges and universities is 18.37:1, of which, vocational (College) colleges 20.28:1.¹ With the continuous development of vocational education, the quality problems of vocational education begin to appear, and the level of vocational teachers is partially out of gear. *The 2016 National Evaluation Report on the Competency of Higher Vocational Colleges to Adapt to Social Needs* (2016) puts forward some problems in teachers that are "the professional construction capacity of some colleges and universities is weak. The number of full-time teachers in some professional points is less than 2, and some professional points have no full-time teachers."² Specifically, some teachers in China's Vocational Colleges directly enter the posts of Vocational Colleges after graduation. These teachers have advanced theoretical knowledge but insufficient practical experience; some elder teachers have good teaching competency, but lack new knowledge, new methods and new skills; some teachers have strong practical competency, but lack of teaching experience and encounter difficulties in imparting knowledge. The teaching level and practical competency of teachers in Vocational Colleges play a vital role in whether Vocational Colleges can cultivate qualified and excellent vocational and technical talents. The state has provided a lot of financial and material support for training high-level teachers in Vocational Colleges. At the same time,

the government has also formulated policy documents to standardize teacher training in Vocational Colleges and promote the quality improvement of teachers in Vocational Colleges.

I. Concept overview

1. Learning motivation theory

In the middle and late 19th century, the research on motivation in the field of psychology gradually deepened, and various schools of motivation theories began to appear. More representative motivation theories include instinctive motivation view, S-R motivation view, humanistic motivation view, achievement motivation theory, cognitive evaluation theory, goal orientation theory, reversal theory and so on. With the continuous development of motivation research, the theoretical connotation of learning motivation is gradually enriched.

At present, learning motivation theories include reinforcement theory, achievement motivation theory, social learning theory, attribution theory, competency self-perception theory, achievement goal theory, demand hierarchy theory and so on.

Chen Qi and Liu Rude (2007) pointed out that learning motivation does not affect learning through direct involvement in the process of cognitive construction, but through the awakening of learning emotional state, the enhancement of learning preparation, the concentration of learning attention and the improvement of learning will.⁵Tao Wei (2012) pointed out that learning motivation refers to the internal motivation to stimulate and maintain individual learning activities and make activities towards specific learning goals. It is a kind of achievement motivation.⁶

Based on learning motivation theory, this paper analyzes the current situation of teachers' practical competency in vocational colleges, which can be divided into external motivation and internal motivation. Internal motivation mainly refers to the innate tendency of individual teachers to pursue novelty and challenge, develop and exercise their own competency for exploration and learning. External motivation mainly refers to the social environment that can stimulate and promote internal motivation, including national policies, vocational colleges, enterprises and so on.

2. Practical Competency

At present, there are many studies on practical competency, but there is not a clear and unified concept for the final definition of practical competency, and the understanding of practical competency is also different in different industries and fields. Many scholars have put forward their own views on the definition of teachers' practical competency in vocational colleges.

Wang Na(2019) believes that practical teaching competency is a comprehensive education and teaching competency based on solid theoretical knowledge and displayed in solving the specific problems of the job. It is the unity of professional teachers completing their own teaching tasks and improving students' practical operation competency in the process of practical teaching.⁷

Fu Yipan (2019) believes that under the background of modern vocational education in the construction of "double high", the requirements for teachers' practical teaching competency in the construction of teachers in vocational colleges are mainly reflected in: first, having practical experience in relevant industries or enterprises, and being familiar with the technical development of relevant majors and the skill requirements of professional posts; Understand relevant technical skills and management standards of industry enterprises. The second is to have the professional competency and operation skills specified in the national vocational qualification (skill) standards, as well as the competency of comprehensive teaching competency, skill guidance and skill practice evaluation. The third is to master the role competency of practical teaching instructors. They should have the curriculum practical teaching content that meets the skill needs of professional posts in the industry (project) design and implementation competency, organization competency of practical teaching activities, guidance competency of practical operation and evaluation competency of skill practice. Fourth, have the practical guidance competency of adaptive learners at different levels. Fifth, teachers in vocational colleges have the competency of both professional teaching and enterprise management and technical research.⁸

Ma Qingqing (2019) pointed out that practical teaching competency mainly refers to the teaching objectives achieved by teachers based on personal hands-on competency and teaching competency in the process of practical teaching. Among them, teachers' own practical competency is an important basis for practical teaching competency, and practical skills are the key carrier of teaching competency. Teachers need to improve students' practical competency as the basis and goal.⁹

Guo Zhirong (2020) believes that practical teaching competency is the organic combination of theoretical literacy and practical operation level, including practical operation competency and theoretical teaching competency, and is the organic unity of theory and practice.¹⁰ Zhang Wenying et al.(2020) believe that the main contents of practical competency include: demonstration operation, strong hands-on competency, guiding students' teaching training and post training, personally or guiding students to participate in skill display and competition, and being able to carry out the construction of training room and practice base.¹¹

In Dai Hairong's view (2021), the practical competency and literacy that vocational college teachers should have include practical guidance competency, problem-solving competency, practical reflection competency and innovation competency.¹²

After summarizing the relevant research, the author believes that the practical competency of vocational college teachers includes four dimensions: teaching practice competency, operation practice competency, guiding practice competency and enterprise practice competency. Among them, teaching practice competency mainly refers to the competency of teachers to effectively combine practical experience with theory; Operational practice competency refers to the competency of teachers to find and solve problems in practical operation; The competency of guiding practice refers to the competency of teachers to guide and demonstrate students in practice; Enterprise practical competency refers to the competency of teachers to accept new technologies and ideas when they practice and learn in the enterprise. Their relationship can be shown in the figure below.

3. Current situation of professional practice competency of teachers in Vocational Colleges

From March 2019 to April 2019, the author randomly distributed 794 questionnaires on the practical competency of vocational college teachers to Chinese vocational college teachers, and 629 valid questionnaires were recovered. The questionnaire designs relevant questions from the aspects of teaching practice competency, operation practice competency, guiding practice competency and enterprise practice competency. The results of the questionnaire reflect the current situation of teachers' practical competency in vocational colleges to a certain extent.

3.1 Unreasonable structure of teachers

Among the 629 valid respondents, teachers over the age of 50 account for less than 5%, and about 85% of teachers have bachelor degree or above. Among the teachers interviewed, only 49.44% had practical work experience in professional related fields; The number of direct teachers after graduation accounted for 48.33%, and only 6.2% were transferred from enterprises.(Figure 2) it can be seen that at present, although the teachers in vocational colleges tend to be young and highly educated.

Figure 1

Even if the teachers are young and knowledgeable, their lack of enterprise practical experience is still prominent. In fact, less than half of the teachers have practical experience in enterprises.

Have practical work experience in professional related fields

Figure 2

From the perspective of personnel relations with the school, the number of staff teachers accounts for 52.15%, the number of contract teachers 42.13%, and the number of part-time teachers only accounts for 5.72%.(Figure 4) such personnel relations are likely to reduce the professional security and professional identity of some teachers.

After graduation to participate in recruitment directly teach	304		48.33%
Transferred from another school	280		44.52%
Transferred by the company	39		6.2%
Other way	6		0.95%

Figure 3

No matter from the age structure or the structure of teachers' personnel relations, there are some problems that cannot be ignored in the composition structure of teachers in Chinese vocational colleges.

3.2 The level of mastering practical competency is uneven

The problem of uneven levels of teachers' mastery of practical competency can be clearly seen in the results of the questionnaire. Firstly, this imbalance is reflected in the teaching practice competency. The survey found that 65.18% (Q1) of the teachers could design the teaching situation and teaching process basically or completely based on the working process of professional posts; 64.07% (Q2) of the teachers were able to basically or completely control the teaching and practical effect; Only 40.7% of teachers can basically or completely use modern technical means to carry out practical teaching (Q3); 56.68% of the teachers were able to improve their teaching work basically or completely according to the practical teaching situation (Q4). (Figure 5) modern technology is rapidly updated, and students' learning in practical teaching is not the same. Teachers must keep pace with the times in order to teach students the most advanced ideas and technologies and cultivate high-quality technical talents to meet the requirements of the times.

Title \ Options	1 Not at all	2 Basically does not meet	3 Not sure	4 Basically	5 Fully compatible
Q1	33(5.25%)	45(7.15%)	141(22.42%)	315(50.08%)	95(15.10%)
Q2	37(5.88%)	41(6.52%)	148(23.53%)	321(51.03%)	82(13.04%)
Q3	33(5.25%)	46(7.31%)	294(46.74%)	109(17.33%)	147(23.37%)
Q4	36(5.72%)	50(7.95%)	138(21.94%)	250(39.75%)	155(24.64%)

Figure 4

Compared with the teaching practice competency, the situation of the interviewed teachers is roughly similar. Among the interviewed teachers, 62.95% were able to apply professional theoretical knowledge to practical operation basically or completely scientifically (Q5); 63.12% (Q6) teachers can basically or completely solve the problems encountered in practical operation in professional teaching; 63.55% (Q7) teachers can basically or completely master the use, maintenance and repair of equipment and instruments required in teaching. (Figure 6) teachers' operational and practical competency is the key to teachers' practical competency. The lack of operational and practical competency will restrict the development of teachers' competencies in all aspects. Only talking on paper cannot do practical operation well, so it is difficult for teachers to teach students real talent and practical learning.

Title \ Options	1 Not at all	2 Basically does not meet	3 Not sure	4 Basically	5 Fully compatible
Q5	44(7.00%)	50(7.95%)	140(22.10%)	361(57.39%)	35(5.56%)
Q6	43(6.84%)	43(6.84%)	146(23.21%)	237(37.68%)	160(25.44%)
Q7	37(5.88%)	50(7.95%)	141(22.42%)	116(18.44%)	285(45.31%)

Figure 5

An excellent vocational college teacher not only needs to have rich theoretical knowledge and solid practical competency, but also needs to be able to correctly and effectively guide students to practice. The problems of the interviewed teachers in guiding practical competency need to be solved urgently. 61.8% (Q8) of the teachers who can basically or completely effectively guide students' professional operation practice in the training

course;61.69% (Q9) of the teachers basically or completely have the competency to guide the skills competition inside and outside the school;62% (Q10) of the teachers can give basic or complete effective guidance to students' off campus practice.(Figure 7) students' practical operation, especially off campus practice, is a process they must go through before they go to work. In practical operation, students may encounter various problems, and teachers' timely and correct guidance is very important for them.

Title \ Options	1 Not at all	2 Basically does not meet	3 Not sure	4 Basically	5 Fully compatible
Q8	42(6.68%)	39(6.20%)	153(24.32%)	178(28.30%)	217(34.50%)
Q9	43(6.84%)	45(7.15%)	153(24.32%)	179(28.46%)	209(33.23%)
Q10	36(5.72%)	47(7.47%)	156(24.80%)	172(27.34%)	218(34.66%)

Figure 6

Vocational teachers should go down to the enterprise and practice in the actual posts of the enterprise, turn theory into practice, and test whether what they have learned is correct. In this process, vocational teachers' competencies in all aspects can be exercised, and they can also find problems in front-line jobs, so as to trigger thinking and stimulate research interest. The survey results show that students and vocational teachers' practical competency in enterprises is not ideal. The survey shows that 62.16% (Q11) of teachers are basically or completely familiar with the specific contents of enterprise related professional post knowledge, operation and management;64.03% (Q12) of the teachers who are basically or fully competent for relevant posts and complete skill learning tasks in the enterprise; Only 41.97% (Q13) of teachers were able to basically or completely learn new practical knowledge, new methods, new skills and new processes of relevant majors;63.59% (Q14) of the teachers were able to improve their teaching plans basically or completely in combination with enterprise employment standards and production practice.(Figure 8) it can be seen that about 60% of teachers can better adapt to enterprise practice, and even less than half in some cases.

Title \ Options	1 Not at all	2 Basically does not meet	3 Not sure	4 Basically	5 Fully compatible
Q11	40(6.36%)	43(6.84%)	155(24.64%)	178(28.30%)	213(33.86%)
Q12	43(6.84%)	39(6.20%)	145(23.05%)	193(30.68%)	209(33.23%)
Q13	37(5.88%)	44(7.00%)	284(45.15%)	111(17.65%)	153(24.32%)
Q14	40(6.36%)	58(9.22%)	131(20.83%)	374(59.46%)	26(4.13%)

Figure 7

Overall, the average proportion of teachers who can basically or completely realize the corresponding problems of various competencies is about 60%, only reaching the pass line. If we study carefully, we will find that the average proportion of teachers who can fully meet the competency requirements in the questionnaire is about 30%. The current situation of respondents' practical competency in four aspects reflects the current problems of teachers' practical competency in Chinese vocational colleges to a certain extent, and the solution of these problems is imminent.

III. Constraints on the improvement of teachers' practical competency in Vocational Colleges

1. Teachers' internal drive is insufficient

The lack of teachers' practical competency and teachers' insufficient attention to practical competency are the most important factors restricting the improvement of their practical competency. Young teachers who have just entered the school need to adapt to the new teaching and working environment. Under the pressure of teaching and scientific research, it is often easy to ignore the cultivation of practical competency. Although some teachers have high practical competency, they receive less education and training, so they don't know how to impart practical knowledge to students and transfer what they have learned through teaching. Some part-time teachers need to complete other tasks and cannot devote themselves to teaching. At the same time, these teachers have limited time and are difficult to meet the teaching requirements of vocational colleges.

Among these teachers, some teachers have a certain level of theoretical knowledge, but they can't do anything in practical application, and can't combine their own theoretical knowledge with the actual situation. Some teachers' educational competency and new theoretical research have stagnated, and there are no positive attempts to carry out new knowledge, new methods and new skills. Li Min (2021) pointed out that many teachers cannot clearly describe the difference between vocational education and general education cannot

highlight the “professional” characteristics of Vocational Education in teaching, and the training effect of students’ professional competency is not ideal. This phenomenon is also reflected in the teaching methods of higher vocational teachers, that is, most teachers are still willing to take the teaching method of speaking theoretical knowledge first and then operating.¹³ Hu Yuanqing and Luo Xingling (2021) also found that teachers have problems in enterprise practice: lack of industrial practical work experience and experience, no practical work experience in production and operation, unable to dynamically grasp the current situation and trend of industrial development, and unable to be competent for education and industry, schools and enterprises, professional settings and professional posts, curriculum materials and professional standards The need of deep connection between teaching process and production process.¹⁴

“Emphasizing theory and neglecting practice” or “having theory and difficult to practice” have greatly hindered the improvement of teachers’ practical competency. Only by changing teachers’ ideas and fundamentally making teachers realize the importance of practical competency can we change the situation.

2. There are some misunderstandings in the assessment system of vocational colleges

The whole society has great hopes for vocational education, so it also has high expectations for teachers in vocational colleges. However, the reality is that even if the state continues to issue relevant policies, clarify the important position of Vocational Education in the whole education system, and issue various rules and regulations to ensure the construction of vocational education teachers, most people in the society still have misunderstandings about the construction of teachers in vocational colleges.

Some colleges and universities in Vocational Colleges Teachers’ practical competency assessment system is not perfect, which has hit the enthusiasm of teachers. To some extent, this also affects teachers in vocational colleges. Wang Chengguang (2021) pointed out that the recruitment of professional teachers in higher vocational colleges is still carried out according to the conditions of theoretical teaching competency, and there is no control over their practical competency. Most of the new professional teachers are college graduates, lacking enterprise training and strong practical operation competency. There are no clear requirements for the management of professional teachers’ practice and exercise process in enterprises. It depends entirely on the personal application of professional teachers. Most of them have formalism and deal with it in order to complete the task.¹⁵ NongSiqi (2017) found that few of the existing higher vocational colleges can establish a perfect teaching practice teaching competency training system, cannot actively promote the improvement and establishment of various measures, the existing teaching facilities cannot meet the requirements of teachers to improve their personal practical teaching competency, and lack a good learning atmosphere and learning environment.¹⁶ Li Jianrong, & Wang Tingjun (2020) also pointed out that for a long time, due to the wrong ideological guidance of “emphasizing theory and neglecting skills” and “emphasizing level and neglecting type”, teachers in higher vocational colleges have not deviated from the common characteristics of teacher evaluation in undergraduate colleges in terms of professional title evaluation and annual assessment, paid too much attention to theoretical teaching and teaching and scientific research achievements, and paid insufficient attention to practical teaching skills and results, It is difficult to meet the requirements of talent training in higher vocational colleges because it does not reflect the professional and practical characteristics of higher vocational teachers and lacks the professional characteristics of higher vocational teachers.¹⁷

The current assessment system of vocational colleges is similar to that of ordinary colleges and universities. It lacks the assessment of professional practical competency and focuses on academic research. Therefore, teachers will not pay attention to the improvement of professional practical competency, which is inconsistent with the goal of vocational education. At present, the salary distribution of many vocational colleges is mainly determined by the number of substitute hours of teachers. Therefore, teachers will focus on the increase of class hours and ignore the improvement of teaching quality, which has a direct negative impact on the development of teachers’ professional practice competency.

3. The teacher training system is not perfect

The imperfect teacher training system is first reflected in the lack of teacher training conditions. Guan Lili (2021) mentioned that ordinary colleges and universities are responsible for the construction of training bases. Due to the lack of in-depth and systematic understanding of vocational education, ordinary colleges and universities lack relevant experience in vocational education teacher training, which is less matched with the vocational education teacher training model.¹⁸ In addition, the teaching reform of “integration of industry and education” has also been promoted for some time, but many colleges and universities are still unable to guarantee the training origin and equipment. Cai Jun, & Ji Jianhua (2021) mentioned that due to the lack of experimental training equipment, some courses offer limited experimental training courses; Practical teaching hours and theoretical teaching hours are treated differently, so it also affects teachers’ enthusiasm for practical teaching to a certain extent. The lack of teachers’ practical competency also makes some experimental training teaching become the deepening and extension of theoretical teaching, rather than the real cultivation of students’ vocational skills.¹⁹

Secondly, teachers' enterprise practice is a mere formality. Most of the teachers in vocational colleges are fresh graduates of colleges and universities and lack practical experience in their majors. In view of this phenomenon, schools should strengthen the training of young teachers and create opportunities for teachers to practice in enterprises. Enterprise practice is an important way to improve teachers' professional practice competency. However, according to the survey, the enterprise practice of teachers in some vocational colleges in China cannot be effectively guaranteed. Wang Yanfen (2021) pointed out that school enterprise cooperation lacks depth and breadth, and the interests of both sides have different demands. Teachers take a horse and watch fancy practice, and their scientific research competency and service level are limited, which cannot solve technical problems for enterprises. As a result, industry enterprises are unwilling to spend time and cost to participate in the training of "double qualified" teachers, and enterprises are unwilling to accept the practice of vocational teachers.²⁰ Yang Fan (2020) believes that at present, due to the lack of in-depth cooperation between schools and enterprises, the production problems and scientific research problems faced by enterprises cannot obtain the assistance of colleges and universities, which greatly weakens the motivation of enterprises' cooperation and is unwilling to invest too much energy in teacher training.²¹ The short time of enterprise practice and lack of continuity make it difficult for teachers to deeply learn the advanced technology of relevant majors in a short time, which is also one of the reasons why it is difficult to substantially improve teachers' professional practice competency.

IV. Countermeasures for improving teachers' practical competency

1. Change teachers' ideas

From a subjective perspective, new knowledge is an indispensable part of the improvement of teachers' practical competency, and we should pay high attention to the promotion strategies and methods, otherwise it will easily lead to the backwardness of future education and serious derailment. Teachers themselves need to change their ideas and realize that career development is not just papers and professional titles. Only by mastering cutting-edge technologies and contacting the front line can they provide more ideas for their teaching and scientific research and open their horizons. In addition, vocational teachers also need to be clear that their ultimate task of teaching is to cultivate high-quality technical talents who can solve problems and find innovation in practical work. Only vocational college teachers themselves have a strong sense of practice, their practical competency can be really improved, and students can really benefit.

From an objective point of view, all parties need to coordinate with each other to provide sufficient guarantee for teachers to improve their practical competency. The state needs to further standardize the content of teachers' practical competency training in Vocational Colleges and refine the objectives. The state can actively organize all kinds of teachers' practical skills competitions at all levels to truly realize "promoting reform through competition". The state can also integrate all forces, break regional differences, balance practice resources, promote the formation of alliances among vocational colleges, build e-learning and training platforms, and realize the purpose of excellent schools driving backward schools and resource sharing. Social recognition and policy support will become a strong backing for teachers' self-improvement in vocational colleges.

It is difficult for teachers to create so many practical learning opportunities by themselves. Vocational colleges should create and provide opportunities for teachers to learn. Liu Feng, & Zhou Zhaoyu (2021) believes that vocational colleges should actively create opportunities for professional teachers to go out for training and communication, so that teachers can be exposed to the latest cutting-edge knowledge, skills or ideas. Common training and exchanges include academic conferences, teacher training, professional skills training, international exchanges, etc.²²

2. Improve teacher introduction and evaluation mechanism

The main goal of vocational education is to cultivate students into high-quality technical talents. Teachers, as teachers of professional skills, should have rich industry experience and skilled operation skills.

According to the implementation plan of national vocational education reform, from 2019, professional teachers in Vocational Colleges and Application-oriented Undergraduate Colleges and universities will be recruited openly from personnel with more than 3 years of enterprise work experience and higher vocational education, Special highly skilled talents (including those with vocational qualification above senior worker) can appropriately relax the educational requirements, and will not be recruited from fresh graduates from 2020.²³

The selection of recruitment sources should be based on the talent training objectives of the school and the specific needs of the post. In addition to the requirements for the examination of academic qualifications and professional knowledge, attention should also be paid to the examination of their relevant enterprise work experience, professional qualification level certificates, etc. Only by strictly stipulating the relevant standards of teacher employment from the introduction of teachers and strengthening the assessment of teachers' professional practice competency can we ensure the professional quality of teachers in vocational colleges.

A fair and reasonable teacher assessment and evaluation mechanism can fully mobilize teachers' enthusiasm. Vocational colleges should improve the evaluation mechanism of teachers, such as integrating teachers'

enterprise practice, social services and technological innovation into the evaluation system, so as to improve the evaluation mechanism of teachers. Teachers who have achieved their goals are fully rewarded, teachers are encouraged to actively improve their professional practice competency, and vocational teachers' professional practice competency is improved through a fair and reasonable assessment system.

3. Deepen school enterprise cooperation

School enterprise cooperation and the integration of industry and education are not only the school running characteristics of vocational education, but also the main path to improve the professional practice competency of teachers in vocational colleges. In the national vocational education reform implementation plan issued by the Ministry of education in 2019, teachers in vocational colleges are required to carry out five-year rotation training, and explore the establishment of a one-year educational internship for new teachers and a three-year enterprise practice system.²³ At the same time, the national vocational education reform implementation plan also requires vocational college teachers to carry out a five-year cycle of full rotation training, and explore the establishment of a one-year educational internship for new teachers and a three-year enterprise practice system.²³ In addition, the Ministry of education and other seven departments jointly issued the notice on the provisions on enterprise practice of teachers in vocational schools. It is required that "vocational schools should protect the right of teachers to participate in enterprise practice regularly. Educational administrative departments at all levels and vocational schools should formulate specific measures to constantly improve the system of teachers' regular practice in enterprises. Enterprises should also accept vocational school teachers to practice in enterprises according to law."²⁴

Wang Congxia (2020) believes that we should focus on the positioning and needs of the school enterprise cooperative talent training mode, constantly improve the openness and sharing of the construction of teaching staff in higher vocational colleges, and fully mobilize the enthusiasm of government functional departments, higher vocational colleges and enterprises.²⁵ Teachers entering enterprises can learn new technologies and knowledge of the industry. By improving their professional practice competency, they can effectively guide students' professional operation practice and effectively improve the quality of education. Therefore, promoting the in-depth cooperation between schools and enterprises is the key to improve the professional practice competency of teachers in vocational colleges.

V. Summary

With the development of China's economy, the industry has an increasing demand for technical talents. Based on this, Vocational Colleges have expanded their enrollment on a large scale, and vocational education has developed unprecedentedly. At present, vocational education has become an important part of higher education in China. With the expansion of vocational education, there are many problems in its school running quality and teaching level, which has attracted extensive attention from all walks of life.

Teachers are the main body of training talents in Vocational Colleges, especially in the context of the integration of industry and education, teachers' professional practice competency plays a key role in improving the overall school teaching quality. China can improve teachers' practical competency according to diversified measures and standards. The problems appearing in the competency improvement can also be solved according to correct measures and standards. The introduction of relevant educational norms also helps to achieve better teaching results, and the value created on the whole is also prominent. In the future, in terms of improving teachers' practical competency, we should continue to make scientific and reasonable improvements according to the actual situation of each specialty, grasp the development trend of vocational education, and optimize the talent training according to the purpose of the integration of industry and education.

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